

Pedagogical Possibilities Of Teaching Music Theory In The Higher Education System

Ibrokhimjonova Gavkhar Amanbaevna

International Nordic University,

Associate professor of the Department of "Music Education"

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Abstract: This article analyzes the pedagogical possibilities of teaching music-theoretical disciplines (solfedgio, music theory, harmony, polyphony, music form analysis, etc.) in higher education institutions from a theoretical and methodological perspective. Our research highlights the role of music-theoretical disciplines in the formation of professional competence of future music teachers and performers, their importance in developing musical thinking, auditory culture and creative abilities.

Keywords: higher education, music education, professional competence, musical thinking, auditory culture, interactive methods, innovative technologies.

Introduction

In today's conditions of globalization and digital transformation, the requirements placed on the higher education system are changing radically. In particular, the issue of developing not only the performing skills of future specialists in the field of music education, but also their theoretical knowledge, musical thinking and pedagogical competence is gaining relevance. From this point of view, music theory disciplines constitute the methodological basis of music education in the higher education system and have important pedagogical opportunities in the professional formation of students.

Music theory disciplines - solfedgio, music theory, harmony, polyphony, analysis of musical forms and genres - are the basic disciplines in the formation of musical hearing, musical thinking and artistic and aesthetic taste in students. Through these disciplines, the student understands the internal structure of a musical work, perceives the logical connections between sounds, and masters the musical text on the basis of an analytical and creative approach. It is this process that determines the pedagogical potential of music theory disciplines.

In higher education practice, teaching music theory disciplines is often perceived as complex and theoretically difficult disciplines. This creates the need not to be limited to traditional approaches in teaching them, but to use active and interactive methods focused on the student's personality. The educational process, organized on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies, digital tools, integrative and competency-based approaches, significantly increases the effectiveness of mastering music-theoretical disciplines. At the same time, ensuring their inextricable

connection with performing disciplines in the process of teaching music-theoretical disciplines is of pedagogical importance. The combination of theory and practice forms the ability of students to apply musical knowledge in real performing activities, develops independent analysis, musical thinking and a creative approach. This is one of the important conditions for improving the quality of music education in higher education.

Identifying the pedagogical possibilities of teaching music-theoretical disciplines in the higher education system, improving them based on modern educational requirements, and effectively introducing them into the educational process is one of the important scientific and practical tasks facing today's music pedagogy. This article analyzes these issues from a scientific and pedagogical point of view.

Theoretical basis

Theoretically substantiating the issue of teaching music-theoretical subjects in the higher education system requires, first of all, considering the fundamental concepts of music pedagogy - education, upbringing, musical thinking, auditory culture and professional competence - as a single system. Music-theoretical subjects are aimed at understanding the internal laws of musical art, through which students develop the ability to perceive, analyze music and draw conclusions based on musical thinking. From the point of view of pedagogical theory, music-theoretical subjects are interpreted as subjects that combine the cognitive, affective and psychomotor components of the cognitive process. While the cognitive approach ensures the mastery of musical concepts, terms and theoretical knowledge, the affective component forms an aesthetic attitude towards music and emotional perception, and the psychomotor factor develops musical hearing, intonation and rhythmic sensations. This triad is the main theoretical model that determines the pedagogical possibilities of music-theoretical disciplines.

In modern educational theory, the competency approach is considered one of the important theoretical foundations of teaching music-theoretical subjects. In this approach, the priority is not only for the student to have knowledge, but also to be able to apply it in practical activities, think independently and make creative decisions. Music-theoretical subjects create a favorable pedagogical environment for the formation of these competencies, as they require analytical thinking, working with musical text and a scientific approach to musical phenomena.

Also, the integrative approach is one of the important factors enriching the theoretical basis of music-theoretical subjects. In this approach, theoretical subjects are inextricably linked with performing, conducting and pedagogical subjects, creating a single educational space. As a result, the student perceives music not as a

set of separate subjects, but as a holistic artistic and pedagogical system. Integration ensures a deeper assimilation of musical knowledge and its application in practice.

The activity-oriented approach in music pedagogy also constitutes an important theoretical foundation for teaching music-theoretical subjects. This approach assumes that the student is not a passive listener, but an active subject of the educational process. Through musical analysis, solfedgio singing, improvisation and creative exercises, theoretical knowledge is strengthened in the process of activity. This is an important pedagogical factor that increases the effectiveness of music-theoretical subjects. Thus, the theoretical foundations of teaching music-theoretical subjects in the higher education system are formed on the basis of the mutual harmony of music pedagogy, educational theory and modern didactic approaches. These theoretical foundations allow for a systematic, goal-oriented and effective organization of the music education process and serve to ensure the professional and creative development of future specialists.

Methodological basis

The methodological basis of this study is based on the fundamental ideas and principles of modern pedagogy, music education theory and higher education didactics. The study considers the process of teaching music theory as a holistic pedagogical system, in which the goals, content, methods, means and results of education are analyzed in their interconnectedness. This approach serves to determine the effectiveness of the music education process and reveal its pedagogical possibilities.

The methodological basis of the study is a systematic approach. Based on this approach, music theory is studied not as separate subjects, but as a component of a single educational system serving the professional formation of a future music specialist. A systematic approach makes it possible to determine the cause-and-effect relationships between the content of music theory knowledge, the stages of its mastery and educational results.

The research also uses a competency-based approach as a leading methodological principle. This approach is aimed at the formation of professional, musical-analytical and pedagogical competencies in students through music theory. In this case, the integral connection of theoretical knowledge with practical activities, the development of students' skills of independent analysis, musical thinking and decision-making based on a creative approach are of paramount importance.

An individual-oriented approach also plays an important role in the methodological basis. This approach involves organizing the educational process taking into account the individual capabilities, level of musical preparation and

creative potential of the student. The use of differential and individual approaches in teaching music-theoretical subjects has a positive effect on the deep and conscious assimilation of knowledge by students.

In addition, the activity-oriented approach enriches the methodological basis of the study. According to this approach, musical-theoretical knowledge is formed in the process of the student's direct musical activity. Theoretical concepts are reinforced by practical activity through solfedgio singing, musical analysis, rhythmic exercises, auditory dictations and creative tasks. This is an important methodological factor that increases the effectiveness of the educational process. The study also uses an integrative approach, methodologically substantiates the interrelation of musical-theoretical disciplines with performing and pedagogical disciplines. The integration of theory and practice forms the skills of students to apply musical knowledge to real performing and pedagogical activities and increases the quality of professional training.

Conclusion

The theoretical and methodological analyses conducted show that musical-theoretical disciplines form the foundation of musical education in the higher education system and are of significant pedagogical importance in the professional and creative development of future music specialists. Through these subjects, students systematically develop musical thinking, auditory culture, analytical thinking, and the skills of applying musical knowledge in practical activities. Also, the use of interactive methods, creative tasks, and modern educational technologies in the process of teaching music-theoretical subjects is significant in that it enhances students' motivation for learning, increases their activity and participation in the learning process. This creates important pedagogical opportunities for ensuring the quality of education and forming the professional competence of future specialists. In conclusion, it should be noted that improving the content and methodology of teaching music-theoretical subjects in the higher education system based on modern educational requirements, enriching them with digital and innovative pedagogical technologies is one of the priority areas of music education development. Research and practical experiments conducted in this area will serve to further improve the quality of music education and raise the professional training of future music teachers and performers to a new level.

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